

STRATEGIC SALESPERSON'S QUALITY AND CUSTOMER SATISFACTION IN THE HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY: A DIAGNOSTIC INVESTIGATION

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Abstract

Strategic salesperson's quality and customer satisfaction in the hospitality industry was investigated and the specific objectives were to determine the effect of salesperson's selling experience; salesperson's adaptive selling, and salesperson's relationship selling skills on customer satisfaction. The study comprises customers who patronize ethnic restaurants that offer local cuisines in Enugu metropolis whose population is infinite. Cochran's sample size determination formula was adopted and 384 was realized. The survey method was adopted and in selecting the respondents, convenience sampling technique was adopted in which copies of structured questionnaires were distributed to 384 respondents who adequately filled and returned 281 of them. Cronbach's Alpha was used to determine the study's reliability and 0.896 was obtained after a pilot study was conducted by distributing 30 copies of questionnaire to the respondents. Analysis of data was conducted using simple linear regression and the findings revealed that selling experience has a significant positive effect on customer satisfaction. Similarly, it was revealed that adaptive selling has a significant positive effect on customer satisfaction. Finally, it was revealed that relationship selling has a significant positive effect on customer satisfaction. Thus, these independent constructs have proven to be very effective in ensuring customer satisfaction. Hence, the sales managers are encouraged to keep on recruiting salespersons with the requisite skills needed to achieving customer satisfaction and long-lasting relationships.

Keywords: Salesperson, Salesperson's Experience, Adaptive Selling, Relationship Selling, Customer Satisfaction.

INTRODUCTION

In the service industry, the key trajectory for measuring customer satisfaction is the SERVQUAL (Zygiaris et al., 2022; Al-allak & Bekhet, 2011) paradigm, which continues to resonate across academia and many industries across the globe.

The passion for achieving customer satisfaction has left many organizations with no alternative but to develop and sustain service quality and customer-oriented strategies as a pivotal service culture since customer satisfaction lubricates and illuminates businesses. Although customer satisfaction is difficult to attain (Chicu et al., 2019), organizations are judiciously advised to pursue its attainment as customer expectations have consequently risen due to their heightened product and service awareness, shrewdness, and sophistication.

Personal selling is a major marketing communication strategy in which the salespeople play a fundamental mediatory role between the industry and the customer (Chicu et al., 2019). Praswati et al. (2019) observed that salespersons are instrumental in achieving customer satisfaction and overall company sales success despite Inuzuka (2021) allusion that what makes a high-performing salesperson still poses a great challenge to service delivery firms across the globe.

This is due to service employees' ineptitude to guarantee deluxe services and customer satisfaction by closing service gaps. Ideally, customers would naturally become brand advocates, ambassadors, and missionary salespeople for a particular restaurant firm if their expectations are achieved after a memorable experience over a palatable plate of food. However, their expectations have been difficult to accomplish thus leading to customer complaints and widening service gaps. It is quite appalling that as customer expectations increase, service gaps continue to widen without the corresponding employee-customer collaboration to close these gaps (Stringam & Gerdes, 2019; Uduak & Ini, 2018).

Stringam and Gerdes (2019), noted that aside customer gap, other frontline employee gaps exist in the restaurant industry. These gaps include the listening gap, the customer-driven service design and standards gap, the performance gap, and the communication gap (Zeithaml et al., 2018). Expressly, organizations must critically tailor their resources toward closing these gaps by providing packaged lasting solutions that meet customer expectations.

Indeed, while it is said that salespersons are born, it is a truism that they are equally made through effective training. In other words, some are naturally endowed with sales talents and traits necessary for marketing products and services assigned to them. In contrast, some require adequate training to acquire the requisite selling skills to deliver effective selling behaviors.

Despite all these, selling is never easy to execute since Zeithaml et al. (2018) observed that service stinks and can never be perfect since certain salespersons display deviance (Darrat et al., 2013), coupled with consumers' heightened information and knowledge security in a highly competitive and ever-changing marketing environment.

Incidentally, companies in the hospitality industry are seriously interested in recruiting salespeople with the required quality to help them identify customers' problems and provide perpetual solutions to them (Attamah et al., 2023; Uduji & Onwumere, 2013). Experienced salespeople have often succeeded in providing satisfaction to customers through the proactive identification and provision of customers' requirements through adaptive selling approaches.

This approach has attracted repeat purchase behavior, trust, profitable customer relationships, and positive word-of-mouth for many companies. Therefore, shrewd salespersons are needed because the major problems customers are the identification and satisfaction of their needs and wants. Unfortunately, providing the needed satisfaction had posed a serious challenge to businesses given that customers had often complained of salespersons' lackluster and poor service delivery which has resulted in a lack of trust, customer dissatisfaction, negative word-of-mouth, and customer brand switching.

In the restaurant domain, the customer is the hub of every service encounter and continues to dominate every service experience so, they expectedly deserve quality service. Nevertheless, where and when expected services elude them, they will resort to bitter complaints, and when their complaints are inadequately resolved by the frontline staff, the customers feel neglected in the entire service routine process. Customers oftentimes complain about not being given a fair hearing (Ohanagorom et al., 2022) in the service co-creation and co-production exercise as the service personnel tend to provide services in a solitary manner.

Unequivocally, one of the most essential characteristics of service is the co-production or the inseparability aspect which is found inadequate in the restaurant businesses. Interestingly, customers can co-create a service by liaising with the salespersons through adequate communication aimed at serving the right food and drink at the right time in the restaurants. Leszczynski and Zielinski (2013) described the essence of a salesperson's communication as an indispensable salesperson's quality that can improve the relationship between them and the customers.

They noted that where this bond is missing, the customer will begin to experience dejection, lack of confidence, lack of commitment, and dissatisfaction, and may offer negative referrals to potential customers. Without any doubt, customers deserve to be allowed to ask questions about their expected cuisines and such questions equally deserve truthful and convincing answers for services to be provided effectively and efficiently.

Furthermore, Roman and Iacobucci (2009) noted that although the relationship between salesperson's quality and sales performance had mainly been investigated, previous studies had ignored salesperson's quality on customer satisfaction (Ahmad & Akbar, 2020; Siagian et al., 2020; Udayana & Prayekti, 2019).

Despite this, no study to the best of the researchers' knowledge has deployed salesperson's selling experience, salesperson's adaptive selling approach, and salesperson's relationship selling skill in determining their effect on customer satisfaction in the hospitality industry in Nigeria. Against this background, this study makes a valid contribution by closing a literature lacuna having demonstrated the effect of strategic salesperson selling qualities on customer satisfaction in ethnic restaurants in selected hotels in Enugu metropolis.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Salesperson's Service Quality

The conformity of a company's assessment of service with the expectations of its clients is referred to as service quality (Ramya et al., 2019). It is the delivery of quality service and satisfaction to a customer through an effective and efficient delivery of services by the company or its salesperson. The production of quality service in the service factory (servicescape) (Zeithaml et al., 2018), is the sole responsibility of the vanguard salespersons based on the service script, despite the truism that service is interactively co-produced by the service provider, the customer, as well as other customers within the service factory. To achieve this service quality feat, management has to deliver the SERVQUAL model dimensions such as responsiveness, reliability, assurance, empathy, and tangibles through the innovativeness of their frontline sales clerks. Nevertheless, only sales managers with great interactive and human relations skills can be highly impactful on their salespersons (Deeter-Schmelz et al., 2008). Delivering quality service and customer satisfaction is a function of sales organizations' initiative to institute a policy and corporate culture that meets salespersons' expectations by guaranteeing job satisfaction (Friend et al., 2013).

Nonetheless, services according to Ohanagorom et al. (2022) cannot be one hundred percent. However, the company's salespersons have to doggedly work towards achieving exceptional and higher service standards. In respect of this, Agnihotri et al. (2017) advised that the focus of a company's salesperson must be on how to deliver high service quality to enhance customer demand and achieve a higher competitive advantage. They posited that while salespeople still meet their sales quotas, they must provide top-notch services to customers while remaining competitive. Agnihotri et al. (2019) maintained that a higher quality service experience between customers and company salespeople can result seamlessly in improving business and customer performance and relationships. From their point of view, the perception is that service satisfaction breeds profitable and long-lasting relationships between the service provider and the service customer.

Development of Research Hypotheses

In the restaurant business just like any other service business, customer expectations are regularly being truncated, leading to cognitive dissonance and repeated complaints. The discovery of the fact that meeting customer expectation as the epicenter of all marketing practices and the doctrine that organizations must verbigerate and perceive customer satisfaction as being ritually paramount, and the need to pursue it tenaciously via salespersons' ingenuity and dexterity is the purpose of this research. However, based on a thorough examination of current literature, three independent constructs as salesperson's experience, salesperson's adaptive selling approach, and salesperson's relationship selling approach were deployed to evaluate their influences on customer satisfaction (dependent construct) in the restaurant industry.

Salesperson Selling Experience

This is the period an individual has worked in a firm as a professional salesperson (Wardoyo et al., 2019). It is the wealth of knowledge and acumen that a salesperson has accumulated over a long period of interaction with customers, products, companies, and competitors. A salesperson's selling experience has a major role to play in achieving customer orientation (Yeo et al., 2019). A customer's post-purchase experience is a function of a salesperson's professional experience, thus, Adhilla (2015) and Agnihotri et al. (2019) reinforced that a customer gains a memorable experience through salesperson interaction in the course of service delivery. regarding this, El Bayaa et al. (2009) established that an experienced salesperson can effortlessly establish and sustain a profitable long-term sales relationship with customers. This is because when the customer is served professionally, he/she wields a fantastic and memorable service experience that can provoke repurchase behavior and positive word-of-mouth for the company.

Although it is difficult to recruit and retain an experienced salesperson (Hazrati et al., 2012), experience is very important because the more the salesperson gains experience, the more he or she expands their service production and delivery horizon to serve their customers satisfactorily and profitably (Siagian et al., 2020). Although customers may be very stubborn and grumpy to appease, only an experienced salesperson can decoy and motivate them to succumb to certain sales proposals and demonstrations. An experienced salesperson weighs a potential customer's emotional dispositions (Khetjenkarn & Agmapisarn, 2020) and strategically adjusts through difficult selling situations to make his/her sales presentation a success. Realistically, handling customer objections is one of the biggest challenges facing many salespersons and if a salesperson possesses the requisite experience, it would not pose any threat because the salesperson can professionally persuade the customer to buy. In the restaurant business, a frontline sales executive knows what, where, when, and how best to meet the customers' needs. Based on this debate, the researchers propose:

H1: Salesperson's selling experience has a significant effect on customer satisfaction in the hospitality industry.

Adaptive Selling

Intrinsically, the success of a salesperson's interaction and rapport with the customer depends on adaptive selling behavior (Park & Holloway, 2003). Adaptive selling behavior refers to a salesperson's understanding and adequate knowledge of customer's expressed needs and wants by wavering sales situations and behavior to suit them and engender customer orientation strategies (Kaptein et al., 2018; Kara et al., 2013). Buttressing this statement, Kavoozi et al. (2014) stated that salespersons can prove that they possess proper information, understanding, and knowledge about their customers by providing lasting customer satisfaction through the adoption of adaptive selling skills. This selling tactic is provided for customers given that they are unique and must be perceived as such at every point in time.

Indeed, no two persons are the same since even Siamese twins possess different needs and perceive the world differently from a different point of view. Thus, services need not be standardized, since they need to be adapted given that customer "A" must be seen to be quite disparate from customer "B." With this, Okolo et al. (2015) emphasized that companies who engage in international marketing practices need to adopt the adaptation approach against standardization to reaffirm the aphorism - "Do in Rome; as the Romans do." Consequently, salespersons need to psychologically focus their lenses on customers' worldviews, personalities, attitudes, motives, buying habits, buying intentions, and behaviors to serve them optimally.

However, adaptive selling is the art and act of manipulating sales to suit the customer in a typical selling situation. Kaptein et al. (2018) and Rapp et al. (2014) defined adaptive selling as the changes in the course of salesperson-customer interactions consequent upon perceived information regarding the selling situation. It means adjusting the company's or a salesperson's selling approaches to the customer's inner disposition and attributes (Rocco and Whalen). What this implies is that the selling behavior of the salesperson is logically and dramatically adjusted to suit the customer's needs and wants.

It is a strategic approach of applying empathy during customer interaction or engagement to provoke order placement by the customer in a typical selling situation. In line with this, Ahmad and Akbar (2020) posited that it necessitates changing the selling behavior of a salesperson in the course of customer interaction to conquer customer objections and encourage purchase behavior. Ahmad et al. (2021) asserted that adaptive selling makes a salesperson more creative in packaging services for customers. From their viewpoints, it encourages and sustains good relationships with the customer hence improving sales performance. Roman and Iacobucci (2009) reaffirmed that adaptive selling helps in improving the communication and relationship between the customers and the

salesperson aimed at identifying and providing system selling solutions and improved customer satisfaction. Based on this argument, the researchers hypothesize:

H2: Salesperson's adaptive selling behavior has a significant effect on customer satisfaction in the hospitality industry.

Relationship Selling

The establishment and sustenance of good and long-lasting rapport with customers triggers effective business communication. Relationship selling according to El Bayaa et al. (2009) can breed perpetual customer satisfaction. It is a powerful competitive weapon used by an organization to gain a competitive advantage (Ernest 2011). Boles et al. (2000) underpinned that building rock-solid relationships with customers is an integral part of strategic sales management. In their views, previous investigations have proven that the performance of salespeople improved significantly as a result of building long-lasting relationships with customers.

What exposes a salesperson's personality and motivation is his rapport with the sales manager (Nguyen et al., 2019), which in turn is translated into establishing a good relationship with customers. Upon its integration into a sales organization's culture, relationship selling has a record of generating higher revenue for many organizations (Pop et al., 2011). Relationship selling evolved from the relationship marketing concept (El Bayaa et al., 2009). It is a strategic selling technique where the interest of the company is on building and maintaining profitable and lasting relationships with their customers. Pop et al. (2011) supported this adding that companies tend to circumvent the pursuit of one-shot sales by building and maintaining strong, long-lasting, and profitable customer relationships. El Bayaa et al. (2009:8) defined relationship selling "as the personal approach of the sales function, which aims to create and maintain long-term relationships with customers, as opposed to traditional transactional selling."

This selling approach goes beyond selling a product or service by offering credit sales, free delivery, on-the-shop refreshments, giving valid information, etc., to get involved in customers' events such as open houses, weddings, birthdays, burials, anniversaries, naming ceremonies, award-winning occasions, and supporting political candidates by committing the company's resources in one way or the other toward making the events scintillating, memorable and fruitful. In support of this, Nguyen et al. (2022) opined that salespeople who are customer-oriented participate in events that are of high value to their customers because they care.

Incidentally, relationship selling has changed the selling paradigm from the old, traditional, or transactional selling. While the latter focuses on having adequate and technical product knowledge and the company's competencies in delivering sales presentations convincingly in a transactional way, the former focuses on establishing and sustaining value-laden long-lasting relationships with the customers (El Bayaa et al., 2009). Succinctly, relationship selling is a modern paradigm that focuses on a customer-oriented approach to selling, while the old paradigm focuses on a product-oriented approach to

selling. Ernest (2011) concluded that relationship selling is a customer-centric approach that forms a communication nexus between a salesperson and a customer.

El Bayaa et al. (2009) and Boles et al. (2000) illustrated that interactive intensity, cooperative intentions, and mutual disclosure are salesperson's relationship selling indicators. Previous findings revealed that the most productive salespeople were those who recognized the essence of engaging, creating, and sustaining good rapport with the customers to improve sales rather than embarking on one-shot sales. Also, it was revealed the success of 100 top business-to-business salespeople was attributed to their judicious application of relationship selling approach (Ernest 2011). Upon this contribution, the researchers tentatively state:

H3: Salesperson's relationship selling behavior has a significant effect on customer satisfaction in the hospitality industry.

Customer Satisfaction in the Hospitality Industry

Customer satisfaction is paramount to the success of every business organization. Although service is imperfect in manufactured goods and services companies (especially restaurant companies), customers deserve to gain great satisfaction from the services they co-create with the restaurant service providers. Regrettably, dissatisfaction with services leads to customer grievances and complaints which most times might be very arduous to manage. Undoubtedly, customer complaints management helps organizations to make robust service improvements. Also, it is a way of restoring or recovering customer trust and confidence in the firm when services are inadequate, however, when this management is lacking, they tend to spell doom for the organization in question. Agu (2022) in his study revealed that a "sincere apology," which is a recovery strategy had a significant effect on customer satisfaction.

Typically, customer satisfaction is a customer's feeling of physio-psychological equilibrium after the consumption or use of a company's goods or services. It is a powerful weapon for nailing and decoying customers to offer their patronage and repeat patronage in most businesses. That is why Andaleeb and Conway (2006) remarked that customer satisfaction is the marketing nucleus. Although customer satisfaction remains unconquerable in the business world, Adewale et al. (2014) argued that in marketing, customer satisfaction is one of the most studied constructs and refers to it as the matching of a chosen product with consumer expectations. They observed that customer satisfaction is a function of a customer's past service experience with the firm. They also stated that a customer becomes satisfied when exclusive services are rendered by frontline staff. In the restaurant context, it is a balance between a customer's fair perceptions of the actual service delivery and the customer's prior service expectations.

Meritoriously, Parasunaman and his colleagues propounded the SERVIQUAL model for measuring customer satisfaction with services (Stanujkic et al., 2019). Andaleeb and Conway (2006) revealed that the quality of food served and the responsiveness of the frontline service employees had a significant influence on customer satisfaction in the

restaurant industry. They observed that poorly served customers get dissatisfied with the firm's services and may engage potential customers in negative word-of-mouth. Put pithily, Andaleeb and Conway (2006:4) stated that "a disgruntled customer can, thus, become a saboteur, dissuading other potential customers away from a particular service provider."

Assimilation-Contrast Theory of Customer Satisfaction

Consumers possess natural tendencies towards acceptance, rejection, earning satisfaction, and dissatisfaction with the consumption or use of products and services consequent upon their pre-purchase expectations and post-purchase product and service performance and experience. The assimilation-contrast theory is greatly applied in the customer satisfaction literature (Manyara & Mutuku, 2020), given that customers naturally wield expectations whenever they want to purchase a product or service (Ohanagorom et al., 2022). Sometimes, these expectations at one point are cut short and at other times, they are fully actualized. When these expectations are met, the customer experiences satisfaction, whereas when they are not met, they experience cognitive dissonance (dissatisfaction). Surprisingly, when organizations meet customers' needs beyond their expectations, they will be delighted (Kotler et al., 2018).

In the service sector, especially the hospitality industry, firms strive to achieve customer satisfaction via efficient and effective service delivery. Ohanagoron et al. (2022) acknowledged that the quest and aspiration to get the right things done are hard to come to fruition since no service can be hundred percent. However, as true as this statement might be, services businesses must strive to achieve near-hundred percent as a one percent death in a one million heart surgery in a hospital will amount to ten thousand deaths and this could be highly disastrous.

Regrettably, service delivery undoubtedly cannot be undiluted since one of its basic characteristics is variability. Put succinctly, no two services can ever be the same since service providers, service customers, and other customers within the services cape (service atmosphere and environment) are humans and can easily influence service co-creation in the service factory given that they possess different physio-psychological make-up and thus behave differently in different interactional situations. Certainly, these human elements and the services cape in one way or another influence the service delivery architecture.

Since this is true, the attainment of customer satisfaction in the restaurant industry cannot be fully realized since customers will always show their grievances via complaint channels. In other words, customer satisfaction cannot be symmetrical, but asymmetrical; it cannot be balanced but lopsided. Sequel to this, this study will be anchored on the assimilation-contrast theory as the intent of restaurant management would be to render services to the level of customer satisfaction (near perfect services).

In the context of the assessment of customers' exposure to actual service delivery based on their pre-dispositional expectation, the assimilation-contrast theory was propounded

by Anderson (1973), and it stipulated that customers have latitudes of acceptance and rejection (Kokthi & Kelemen-Erdos, 2017) of products and services. Manyara and Mutuku (2020) argued that when product or service performance matches customer expectations, assimilation will occur since the performance falls within a customer's latitude of acceptance. What happens is that the customer literally neglects any discrepancy between expectations and performance even though his/her expectations are cut short.

On the other hand, contrast will prevail if the customer magnifies any discrepancy in the product/service expectations and performance, and so, the product/service will not be accepted given that the performance typically falls within the customer's latitude of rejection. Nneoma and Uwabor (2021) argued that while the assimilation theory suggests that consumers tend to downplay the disparity between expectations relating to product/service performance, the contrast theory on the other hand tends to exaggerate these differences in expectation and performance.

Furthermore, applying this theory to the current study depicts that expectation and performance within the services domain are assessed through post-purchase experiences with the firm (restaurant in this case). Pragmatically, this theory suggests that a customer who possesses the latitude of acceptance for services provided by a salesperson even though the services did not meet his or her expectations, will be satisfied as the discrepancy existing between the services provided by the salesperson and his or her expectations will be disregarded.

On the other hand, the services provided by the salesperson will be rejected if the service provided by the salesperson falls within a customer's latitude of rejection being that the customer magnifies the performance and expectation discrepancy and therefore ends up feeling dissatisfied. The assimilation-contrast theory is considered very apposite for the current study given its applicability to the present study. The conceptual framework for the independent and dependent constructs is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Hypothetical Causal Model

Source: Researchers' Schematics

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The survey method was adopted in this study and a structured questionnaire was administered to the customers to gather primary data from the ethnic/native restaurants in selected restaurants in Enugu metropolis. The scope borders on salesperson's quality and customer satisfaction in the hospitality industry and the target population is infinite and comprises those customers who are patrons of those ethnic/native restaurants that mainly serve local/native cuisines (no fast food not served) in Enugu metropolis. The restaurants were selected conveniently and include Emily Restaurant, Dolphins Restaurant, The Native Pot, Ntachi Osa, Diamond Restaurant, Bush House Arena, Item 7, Mama Onyinye Restaurant, Odi Oku Restaurant, and Bush Bar. The Cochran's formula was used to determine the sample size of 384 customers. However, in assessing the validity of the instrument, content validity was adopted, and two marketing professors and two service industry experts edited and modified the research instrument to ensure that it potently captures the purpose of the study. A pilot study was conducted using 30 respondents across these restaurants and the value of 0.896 was obtained after the test of reliability of the research instrument was conducted using Cronbach's Alpha. The convenience sampling method was adopted for selecting the respondents in the study and out of the 384 copies of the questionnaire distributed, 301 copies were returned, of which 281 were correctly responded to and used for research analysis. The hypotheses were tested using simple linear regression analytical tools with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22.

RESULTS

Data generated from customers of the sampled customers of selected ethnic/native restaurants in Enugu metropolis were presented using descriptive statistics and analyzed using Simple Linear Regression statistical tool. The analysis was done with descriptive and inferential statistics with the aid of SPSS (Version 22).

Table 1: Responses on the effect of salesperson selling experience on customer satisfaction

S/No	Questionnaire items	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Total (Freq)
		Freq	Freq	Freq	Freq	Freq	
1	The salesperson welcomes customers with warm greetings.	98	73	45	35	30	281
2	The salesperson knows customer's kind of food and drink.	89	85	50	23	34	281
3	The salesperson introduces and gives information about new menu to customers.	85	90	45	30	31	281
4	The salesperson gives customers a special treat based on demand.	93	78	31	41	38	281

5	The salesperson provides customers with all round satisfactory sundry services.	96	81	41	38	25	281
6	The salesperson encourages customers to keep patronizing their restaurant.	105	92	32	32	20	281
Total		566	499	244	199	178	1686

Source: fieldwork, 2023.

In table 1, 566 indicated strongly agree, 499 indicated agree, 244 indicated neutrality, 199 indicated disagree and 178 indicated strongly disagree respectively in their responses. This implies that salesperson selling experience has a significant positive effect on customer satisfaction.

Hypothesis One

H1: Salesperson's selling experience has a significant positive effect on customer satisfaction.

Table: 2 Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.977 ^a	.955	.955	.28099	.118
a. Predictors: (Constant), Salesperson's Selling Experience.					
b. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction.					

Table: 3 ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	1424.200	1	1424.200	18038.381	.000 ^b
	Residual	66.400	841	.079		
	Total	1490.600	842			
a. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction.						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Salesperson's Selling Experience.						

Table: 4 Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.031	.028		1.105	.269
	Salesperson's Selling Experience	.976	.007	.977	134.307	.000
a. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction.						

Interpretation

The regression sum of squares (1424.200) is not the same as the residual sum of squares (66.400) as Table 3 reveals, indicating that more of the difference in the dependent variable is not explained by the model. The F statistics significance value of (0.000) is

less than 0.05, showing that the variation explained by the model occurred as a result of chance. In Table 2, R, with 0.977 value R is the correlation coefficient, indicating that salesperson's selling experience has a significant positive effect on customer satisfaction. Similarly, R square - the coefficient of determination shows that 95.5 % of the difference in customer satisfaction is explained by the model. The model of linear regression, 0.28099 indicates that the error of the estimate is low. The value of 0.118 is the Durbin-Watson statistics, which is less than 2 indicating that there is no autocorrelation. Hence, salesperson's selling experience coefficient of 0.977 reveals that there is a significant positive effect of salesperson's selling experience on customer satisfaction. In Tables 4 & 13, the t-value of 134.307 is statistically significant. Hence, the study accepts hypothesis one.

Table 5: Responses on the effect of salesperson’s adaptive selling on customer satisfaction

S/No	Questionnaire items	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Total (Freq)
		Freq	Freq	Freq	Freq	Freq	
1	The salesperson welcomes a customer and asks what the customer needs.	95	81	44	35	26	281
2	The salesperson gives a customer all the information the customer requires.	90	85	41	35	30	281
3	The salesperson ensures that the customer eating table and surroundings are neat.	100	87	36	27	31	281
4	The salesperson monitors the customer closely to ensure that whatever extra needed is provided.	94	91	31	37	28	281
5	The salesperson provides a customer payment options (cash and transfers) even before the meal and drink is served.	99	79	50	28	25	281
6	The salesperson asks the customer for any feedback that can help improve their services.	91	92	43	31	24	281
Total		569	515	245	193	164	1686

Source: fieldwork, 2023.

In Table 5, 569 indicated strongly agree, 515 indicated agree, 245 indicated neutrality, 193 indicated disagree and 164 indicated strongly disagree respectively in their

responses. This implies that salesperson's adaptive selling has a significant positive effect on customer satisfaction.

Hypothesis Two

H2: Salesperson's adaptive selling has a significant positive effect on customer satisfaction.

Table: 6 Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.990 ^a	.981	.981	.18479	.283
a. Predictors: (Constant), Salesperson's Adaptive Selling.					
b. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction.					

Table: 7 ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	1447.831	1	1447.831	42401.395	.000 ^b
1 Residual	28.717	841	.034		
Total	1476.548	842			
a. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction.					
b. Predictors: (Constant), Salesperson's Adaptive Selling.					

Table: 8 Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.092	.019		-4.760	.000
1	Salesperson's Adaptive Selling	1.016	.005	.990	205.916	.000
a. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction.						

Interpretation

The regression sum of squares (1447.831) is not the same as the residual sum of squares (28.717) as Table 7 reveals, indicating that more of the difference in the dependent variable is not explained by the model. The F statistics significance value of (0.000) is less than 0.05, showing that the variation explained by the model occurred as a result of chance.

In Table 6, R, with 0.990 value R is the correlation coefficient, indicating that salesperson's adaptive selling has a significant positive effect on customer satisfaction. Similarly, R square - the coefficient of determination shows that 98.1 % of the difference in customer satisfaction is explained by the model. The model of linear regression of 0.18479 indicates that the error of the estimate is low.

The value 0.283 is the Durbin-Watson statistics, which is less than 2 indicating that there is no autocorrelation. Hence, salesperson's adaptive selling coefficient of 0.990 reveals that there is a significant positive effect of salesperson's adaptive selling on customer satisfaction. In Tables 8 & 13, the t-value of 205.916 is statistically significant. Hence, the study accepts hypothesis two.

Table 9: Responses on the effect of salesperson’s relationship selling on customer satisfaction

S/No	Questionnaire items	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Total (Freq)
		Freq	Freq	Freq	Freq	Freq	
1	The salesperson gives the customer a warm welcome on arrival to their restaurant.	73	79	54	45	30	281
2	The salesperson helps the customer in choosing the correct menu.	74	80	50	43	34	281
3	The salesperson makes sure that everything the customer demanded are fully provided.	80	77	45	51	28	281
		227	236	149	139	92	
4	The salesperson always chats and teases the customer to ensure his/her happiness in the restaurant.	78	78	47	40	38	281
5	The salesperson always asks the customer “I hope you are ok with our meal, drink and service.”	81	69	51	45	35	281
6	The salesperson bids the customer farewell and reminds the customer to always come again.	78	82	47	45	29	281
		237	229	145	130	102	
Total		464	465	294	269	194	1686

Source: fieldwork, 2023.

In Table 9, 464 indicated strongly agree, 465 indicated agree, 294 indicated neutrality, 269 indicated disagree and 194 indicated strongly disagree respectively in their responses. This implies that salesperson relationship selling has a significant effect on customer satisfaction.

Hypothesis Three

H3: Salesperson’s relationship selling has a significant positive effect on customer satisfaction.

Table: 10 Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.992 ^a	.985	.985	.16465	.341
a. Predictors: (Constant), Salesperson's Relationship Selling.					
b. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction.					

Table: 11 ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	1468.428	1	1468.428	54168.869	.000 ^b
	Residual	22.798	841	.027		
	Total	1491.227	842			
a. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction.						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Salesperson's Relationship Selling.						

Table: 12 Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.093	.015		6.027	.000
	Salesperson's Relationship Selling	.972	.004	.992	232.742	.000
a. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction.						

Interpretation

The regression sum of squares (1468.428) is not the same as the residual sum of squares (22.798) as Table 11 reveals, indicating that more of the difference in the dependent variable is not explained by the model.

The F statistics significance value of (0.000) is less than 0.05, showing that the variation explained by the model occurred as a result of chance. In Table 10, R, with 0.992 value is the correlation coefficient, indicating that salesperson's relationship selling has a significant positive effect on customer satisfaction.

Similarly, R square - the coefficient of determination shows that 98.5 % of the difference in customer satisfaction is explained by the model. The model of linear regression of 0.20911 indicates that the error of the estimate is low. The value 0.341 is the Durbin-Watson statistics, which is less than 2 indicating that there is no autocorrelation.

Hence, salesperson's relationship selling coefficient of 0.992 reveals that there is a significant positive effect of salesperson's relationship selling on customer satisfaction. In Tables 12 & 13, the t-value of 232.742 is statistically significant.

Hence, the study accepts hypothesis three. The overall results of the hypotheses testing are shown in Table 13 and Figure II.

Table 13: Summary Results from Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesized Relationship	Hypotheses	Correlation Coefficients	T-Values	Decision
SSE > Customer Satisfaction	H1	0.977	134.307	Supported
SAS > Customer Satisfaction	H2	0.990	205.916	Supported
SRS > Customer Satisfaction	H3	0.992	232.742	Supported

Note- SSE = Salesperson’s selling experience; SAS = Salesperson’s adaptive selling; SRS = Salesperson’s relationship selling.

Figure 2: Results of the Constructs’ Hypotheses

DISCUSSIONS

In the findings, salesperson’s selling experience has a significant positive effect on customer satisfaction as revealed in hypothesis one ($r = 0.977$, $p < 0.05$). What this indicates is that customer satisfaction can easily be achieved if a salesperson delivers food, drink, and other services embellishment that a customer enjoys in the restaurant. This is consistent with the saying that experience matters a lot in everything one does. This is supported by Ahmad and Akbar (2020) as they noted that a salesperson’s selling experience can adapt to a customer’s needs and wants (provision of customer satisfaction), and thus improve customer satisfaction.

In another study, Attamah et al. (2023) found that salesperson performance improved as a result of salesperson selling experience. Also, Johlke (2006) revealed that salesperson's experience has a strong and positive relationship with salesperson's improved performance. Similarly, salesperson's previous selling experience was revealed by Okolo et al. (2016) to have a strong relationship with the operation of a sales force structure.

Also, it was revealed in hypothesis two that salesperson's adaptive selling approach has a significant positive effect on customer satisfaction ($r = 0.990$, $p < 0.05$). This indicates that customers can easily feel satisfied in the restaurant when the salesperson and other employees feel exactly the way the customer feels and hence, provide service along that line. It is the salesperson's display of empathy towards the customer. In support of this, Sutantio et al. (2021) revealed that customer satisfaction was significantly influenced by salesperson's adaptive selling behavior in the housing industry. Similarly, Roman and Iacobucci (2009) revealed that salesperson adaptive selling behavior has a positive relationship with customer satisfaction. Nguyen et al. (2022) underpinned the finding by remarking that customer satisfaction was improved through the practice of adaptive selling behaviors. Therefore, customer satisfaction can be improved when a salesperson adapts selling to the identified needs and wants of the customers in the long run by avoiding customer dissatisfaction in the short run (Yeo, Hur, and Ji 2019) through hasty one-shot sales. In contrast, Agnihotri et al. (2018) reported that the relationship between customer satisfaction and salesperson adaptive selling behavior was not significant. This result shows that adaptive selling approach deployed in selling a group of products and services to the customer was ineffective.

Furthermore, the study showed that relationship selling has a significant positive effect on customer satisfaction ($r = 0.992$, $p < 0.05$). This means that if a salesperson builds and maintains a spirit of camaraderie with their clients, achieving customer satisfaction at every sales encounter will be assured. In consonance with this, El Bayaa et al. (2009) revealed in their study that relationship selling was significantly influenced by variables that generate and improve customer satisfaction. Boles et al. (2000) supported this finding having revealed in their study that interactive intensity, mutual disclosure, and cooperative intention which were the constructs of relationship selling had a significant effect on salesperson performance.

CONCLUSION AND MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS

The findings of this study revealed that selling experience, adaptive selling, and relationship selling respectively had a significant effect on customer satisfaction in the hospitality industry. However, service businesses in the 21st century have experienced unfathomable competition and every restaurant outlet is fighting to have the lion's share of the market.

Interestingly, customers have different needs and wants (requirements) and they look for reputable organizations that can identify these needs and proffer lasting solutions to them.

They naturally have great expectations from service organizations and they doggedly pursue the satisfaction of those expectations.

Hence, when companies fail to match customer expectations with perceived product or service experience, cognitive dissonance will surface leading to dissatisfaction.

Consequently, dissatisfied customers do not return but will switch to competitors and even engage other customers in negative word-of-mouth. All these spell doom for companies and that is why they are beginning to adopt effective strategic selling skills and approaches to help them establish and sustain a win-win relationship with their customers. Thus, salespersons' adequate training is very germane consequent upon the fact that it guarantees the effective and efficient management of customer acquisition, retention, and loyalty in the restaurant industry. Moreover, companies need to be committed and consistent in delivering customer requirements so they can earn their confidence and trust from customers since they naturally surrender their lifetime value to any company that can reliably identify their problems and provide a packaged solution to them. Indeed, loyal customers in their comfort zones will always come back and embark on advanced missionary selling behavior being good ambassadors or advocates (they can vouch for the company) to the company even when things have gone wrong and the image of the company requires resuscitation after being battered in the public eye.

LIMITATIONS AND DIRECTION FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

in the future, this kind of study will be more robust and representative if the scope is enlarged to cover other business cities and geographical areas in Nigeria to assess how restaurant services are delivered in those locations. Secondly, focusing this research on the manufactured goods industry will be very thought-provoking as it will X-ray how salespersons can satisfy their customers in business-to-business dealings in that domain. Thirdly, injecting more selling constructs such as system selling, team selling, and consultative selling will make the study more robust. Finally, using a more advanced data analytical technique like the partial least squares (PLS) structural equation modelling (SEM) will be more rigorous as it will reveal the relationships between the indicators in each construct more.

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Declaration of Interest

The author has no iota of conflict of interest to declare.

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